

Paper 19**IMPLICATIONS OF MEDIA ON SKILL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN****Sushmitha¹ & Pradeep M.D.²**¹ Research Scholar, Institute of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

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ABSTRACT**Purpose:** To showcase how the media is helping children to develop their skills through different shows, and competitions as well as providing training through different media.**Methodology / Design /Approaches:** It is a descriptive study with the help of secondary data where the researchers have conducted a Content Analysis by collecting information from observation and published articles from journals.**Findings and results:** Media play a very important and big role in the life of the children in the present days. Media encourage talents and teach several skills in an innovative way. Children learn better and fast by using media.**Originality/value:** Content analysis of the related works on the skill development of students through media.**Type of Paper:** Conceptual research by using descriptive research design.**Keywords:** Children, Media, Skill development, Reality shows, Quiz, Reels, social media, Television, Newspaper, Movies.**1. INTRODUCTION:**

Media has become part and parcel of every one's life. Media disseminates information and facilitate in providing knowledge. Media provides opportunity to show case their talents through live shows, competitions and events. These shows have become very good platform to show case hidden skills and abilities to public at large. Digital medias such as printing, paintings, designs, graphics, pictures enrich thinking abilities among children. Media also penetrates into ones living space, physical space and relationship building processes in many ways. The walks of life can be better developed in more comprehensive way through the interaction of media in human life. The interest of people in many areas has found a boost through the influence of media [1]. Social media influences the teaching and learning skills. Children can access media information just through the gadgets. By looking into the media children learn to present a matter in a different way in their school or personal life [2]. Since the learning ability among children differs where few kids learn by just listening whereas few others may need to read to understand where as few need both watching and listening to understand. Learning of students also gets influenced by different media including print, radio, and television. So, it is important to understand the type of media which influence more in developing their skills [3]. For example,

animated books help in the education of children by promoting their vocabulary, alphabet knowledge, print concept, rhyme knowledge in kids. Educational programmes telecasted in the television with animation will attract the attention of the kids and influence in the dissemination of knowledge just through the mode of pictures [4]. The media influences in the social, emotional, physical and intellectual development of the children. Reality shows provide a platform, quiz programs aid in improving their knowledge level, few programmes improve the story telling capacity. The information disseminated through the television will lead child towards invention of new things [5]. Kids are growing up in an environment basically with fullest access to knowledge with the help of technology during the 21st Century. Youths are adopting the usage of technology in learning new things and build their abilities. The technological revolution has both mixed good and bad impacts. According to studies, it could potentially have a harmful impact on kids, appearing as aggressive in their behaviour, hazardous sexual behaviour, and substance misuse. There is a need to provide extensive guidelines to use the technology to support their quest for inquiry and how to use the acquired information. It has been noticed that children who connect on various social media sites run a number of risks. Over the decade, the emergence of digital media has increased the usage of media by children in enormous ratio. In 1970, children aged 4 years were found watching the television but now a baby of 4 months starts interacting with the digital media [6]. Under the digital media text, images, audio, and videos are shared. Video games are prepared by fusing traditional and social medias where, artificial intelligence is used where players can virtually "inhabit" created environment and even communicate with other players from distant area. Digital media can thus offer a compelling experience where children's and teenagers' media consumption become highly individualised [7]. The media plays the fundamental role of entertaining the Society. With the variety of stories, media aids in the education [8]. The institutionalization of new media with new forms of media such as radio, motion pictures, and periodicals has started. The manufactured media are profoundly altered by a process known as "social institutionalization." By learning about new communication channels, society adopt new media [9] social media is defined as a person's perception of their capacity to achieve desired results in a social media context [10]. First Industrial Policy which had an initial focus on formal Technical and Vocational Training Education and Training (TVET) sector with dedicated institutions for technical and vocational education. In 1961, the Apprenticeship Act was framed for providing practical training to technically qualified persons in various trades and promoting new skilled manpower. The Indian Education Commission (Kothari Commission) was appointed in 1964 to overhaul the Indian Education Sector by providing policies & guidelines for the development of education in India. The National Labour Policy was framed in 1966. In 1968, the first National Policy on Education was framed. The first Industrial Training Institute (ITI) was set up in 1969 by the Ministry of Labour & Employment (MoLE), Government of India. New National Policy of Education was framed in 1986. The All-India Council of Technical Education (AICTE) was formed in 1987, as the official regulator and funder for polytechnics and technical colleges. The National Policy of Education was modified in 1992. 1990s witnessed the opening up of the economy with substantial growth in IT industry and service sector and relative slowdown in manufacturing and engineering sector. It was felt that a considerable amount of employment for skilled and semi-skilled category workers was to explored outside the traditional trades. With this objective, the National Development Corporation (NSDC) was established in 2008. These paradigm shift resulted in framing of the first National Policy on

Skill Development in 2009 and effort was made to enhance the private partnership to expand the capacity of skills training sector. The National Skills Development Agency (NSDA) was established in 2013 and a vision was casted for a National Qualification Framework (NQF). In 2014, the Apprenticeship Act was amended to include non-engineering as optional trades and Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE) was established. In 2015, the Skill India Mission was launched, the National Policy on Skill Development and Entrepreneurship was framed and the Training and Apprenticeship Division was moved from MoLE to MSDE.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To find the role of media on the skill development of children.
- To find how literacy levels improve in children from media
- To analyse the impact of skill development programmes in electronic media
- To know about the role of social media in children’s skill development
- To suggest parents, understand the advantage and disadvantages of media in their children’s skill development.

3. RELATED STUDIES:

The conceptual analysis in the study is conducted based on the available literature in the areas of “media on skill development of children” by referring to the published works between 2002 to 2022 from the Google scholar consortium.

Area of Study	Observation	Reference
Student and Teacher response to usage of media in Skill Development.	Digital media impact on children’s thinking skills	Collins, L. (2018) [11]
Usage of social media to develop Presentation Skill in the Traditional Classroom	Social media helps children to improve their knowledge	Di Gangi, P. M., Goh, S. H., & Lewis, C. C. (2017) [12]
Interaction of Media, Cognition, and Learning	Skill development of children through print, television and radio	Salomon, G. (2012) [13]
Impact of <u>reading an animated book for emergency literacy skill Development</u>	Skill Development through Animation	Schryer, E., Sloat, E., & Letourneau, N. (2015) [14]
Television and Child Development	Skill development of kids through television programmes	Van Evra, J. (2004) [15]
Non-formal Education on Skill Development	Skill development is high through informal education.	Gupta D and Agarwal S (2018) [16]

The state of the news media	Evolution of media	Mitchell, A., & Holcomb, J. (2016) [17]
Evolution of Media into new media	New media is impactful.	Stöber, R. (2004) [18]
Social media self-efficacy and information evaluation online.	Social Media is impacting on self efficacy	Hocevar, K. P., Flanagan, A. J., & Metzger, M. J. (2014) [19]
<i>Interaction of media, cognition, and learning:</i>	Role of media in education	Salomon, G. (2012) [20]
Using Digital Media to Develop Student Perceptions	Role of media in skill development of students	Harrington, C., & Duncan, N. (2006, May) [21]
Developing Speaking and Citizenship Skills through Radio.	Radio help in learning language	Jaime Osorio, M. F., Caicedo Muñoz, M. C., & Trujillo Bohórquez, I. C. (2019) [22]
Developing students' listening and speaking skills through ELT podcasts.	Podcast helps in developing Listening and Speaking Skills.	Sze, P. M. M. (2006) [23]
Role of educational video cartoon series on digital literacy and resilience for children.	Cartoon helps in improving listening skill.	Martzoukou, K. (2020) [24]
Television and Media Literacy in Young Children	Television helps in improving literacy level.	Jusoff, K., & Sahimi, N. N. (2009) [25]
The effects of literacy messages in an educational television program.	Educational Television Program develop learning skills.	Moses, A. M., Jennings, N. A., Brod, R., Hooker, S. D., Cordell, B., & Sallee, T. (2014) [26]
Positive effects of television on children's social interactions:	Kids social interaction	Mares, M. L., & Woodard, E. (2005) [27]
Effects of Technology on Teaching and Student Learning.	The positive effect of shows on children	Costley, K. C. (2014) [28]
Social Media Support presentation skill development.	Effect of social media	Di Gangi, P. M., Goh, S. H., & Lewis, C. C. (2017) [29]

4. SKILL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH MEDIA:

The use of television, movies and other media for education has increased significantly in recent years. Our fundamental knowledge of how media convey information and which educational objectives they best serve has barely changed. In terms of content, design, and representation aspects, digital media is utilized to collect and manipulate the body and the place. Students document their creative processes and learn how to pick and question their ideas through

continuous process of observation, analysis, and reflection. Informal dialogues with oneself, peers, and tutors, as well as formal evaluations, help students.

(a) Speaking Skill Development: A radio program would allow children to learn language, practice oral skills and develop tolerance and consideration for others. When they visit other countries, it is important to learn the accent where, media will help in the process. Learning language through media will help in education too [30]. Podcasting, a new technology for broadcasting audio programs over the Internet, has seen rapid advancements. Originally, podcasting was used to deliver information and entertainment. However, educators realized the enormous potential of it in teaching and learning. Many writers have emphasized its numerous advantages in language education by developing learners' listening and speaking skills [31] Children enjoy cartoon series. From there they will learn to speak some dialogue. That will improve their listening and speaking capacity. It will lead them to the storytelling skill too. At the age of 2 kids grasping power will improve by seeing videos and listening to stories. The media will be different like radio, podcasts, television, you tube so on [32].

(b) Developing Literacy among Children: Young children's lives revolve around watching television. Mythological stories will reach children easily where they remember the history just over the basis of mythological shows. For example, Raamayana, Mahabharatha, Jansi ki Raani Lakshmi bai. A lesson of ethics can reach easily through the visual treat. Cartoon stories with lessons will create a visual treat in the child's mind and it is very easy to remember too [33] Educational television shows have the ability to boost young children's literacy abilities and attitudes. At the time of the COVID-19 period, students more depend on Doordarshan education-related programmes. And distant education programmes are also provided on radio and television. These days YouTube will provide many education-related channels. Hence, media plays a vital role in developing the literacy level of children [34].

(c) Skills Development through Shows: Reality shows encourage kids to participate in shows or develop that skill. They imitate the characters. Reality shows like Drama Juniors, SAREGAMAPA little champs, Superstar singer, and Kids Master Chef encourage to learn new skills. They will get a platform to prove their talent in small age. Some quiz programs encourage kids to learn more. Some experiments related to education show that will build the interest of the child to know more and that interest leads to the new invention. Children will learn many cultures and new things from the media. Today knowing about any new thing become easy for the child through the use of the internet and new media. So the role of media is high today in a child's skill development [35]

(d) Social Media and Skill Development: Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube are frequently used social media platforms in classrooms. In this study, we concentrate on the re-appropriation of social media in an academic setting to meet learning goals. According to research on social media's educational applications to date, using blogs for writing assignments on social media can significantly contribute to the development of written communication abilities. Children are good at using technology today so they are more into social media. And from there they earn knowledge of what happening as well as many software technologies.

5. MERITS AND DEMERITS OF MEDIA ON CHILDREN'S LIFE:

Media will help the child to understand subject easily. Visual treatment will create a different effect on a child's mind. Getting encouragement and improving talent is possible through media such as television, radio, and social media. Knowledge will be gained easily through media. Equally media will have few demerits to its credit for example, in recent years, some reality shows have shown the extent level of performance but sometimes it will pressurise the child to take more pressure which is not good for their health. Kids may access bad information or restricted information through social medias which may result in bad behaviour. So parents should have access and control over children's internet use.

6. CONCLUSION:

Media creates a huge impact on the children. The usage of media will determine its impact upon the children. By watching and listening media children can improve their listening and speaking skills. Technology gives more opportunities to learn, among them Social Media is the most important one. Children are good at using mobile phones and other digits and they learn and gain knowledge easily. Media plays an important role in the development of children is usage is done in proper and guided ways. Events, competitions, and trainings organised through various media provides ample opportunities to the youngsters to developing their skills. Children need to learn and gain good from media and leave the bad behind. The prudent usage of media is the need of the day.

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